

Realpolitik: The Pragmatic Approach to Politics

Mohammed Saaida

Department of International Relations and Diplomacy, Faculty of Administration Sciences and Informatics, Al-Istiqlal University, Jericho – Palestine.

Email: confador@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7488-9832>

Abstract:

This paper conducts an in-depth examination of the concept of Realpolitik, a pragmatic approach to international relations characterized by the pursuit of national interests. The research encompasses a diverse range of geopolitical contexts, including the United States, Pakistan, Singapore, and Germany, in order to demonstrate the pervasive influence of Realpolitik on global diplomacy. In the 1960s, the US transitioned towards Realpolitik, prioritizing practical engagement over ideological stances. Pakistan's 1970s experiences under General Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq and Singapore's leadership under Lee Kuan Yew demonstrate its adaptability and relevance in achieving national objectives. Realpolitik principles drive successful governance, non-corrupt civil service, and strategic military development. Collectively, these case studies underscore the critical role Realpolitik plays as a framework for diplomacy, emphasizing the importance of practicality and adaptability in navigating the intricate landscape of international relations.

Keywords: Realpolitik, International Relations, Pragmatic Approach, National Interests, Diplomacy, Geopolitical Contexts.

Introduction:

In the complex world of politics and international relations, the concept of Realpolitik stands as a guiding philosophy, emphasizing practicality and the relentless pursuit of national interests. Derived from a rich tapestry of historical origins and contemporary applications, Realpolitik has shaped the course of diplomacy and governance across diverse nations.

This exploration embarks on a comprehensive journey through the realms of Realpolitik, shedding light on its etymology and evolution, its theoretical foundations within political

realism, and the historical figures who have championed its principles. From the enduring tradition of realistic governance in China to Germany's nuanced perspective, from the visionary leadership of Lee Kuan Yew in Singapore to the rejection of utopianism in the United Kingdom, and from the pragmatic evolution in the United States to Pakistan's Realpolitik approach during a critical era – each facet contributes to our understanding of this pragmatic approach to politics.

Realpolitik constitutes a diplomatic and political approach grounded primarily in a pragmatic evaluation of prevailing circumstances and factors, eschewing strict adherence to explicit ideological doctrines or moral and ethical principles. In this regard, it shares philosophical elements with realism and pragmatism, often being succinctly labeled as pragmatism in politics, exemplified by the pursuit of pragmatic or realistic policies.

While historically employed in a predominantly positive or neutral context, since approximately 2014, Realpolitik has been invoked pejoratively to insinuate political strategies perceived as coercive, amoral, or reminiscent of Machiavellian tactics. Eminent advocates of Realpolitik include figures such as Otto von Bismarck, Henry Kissinger, George F. Kennan, Zbigniew Brzezinski, and Hans-Dietrich Genscher, along with statesmen like Deng Xiaoping, Charles De Gaulle, and Lee Kuan Yew.

Etymology and Evolution of Realpolitik: Origins and Early Interpretations

The term Realpolitik finds its origins in the creative mind of Ludwig von Rochau, a prominent German writer and statesman of the 19th century. Rochau's seminal work, "Grundsätze der Realpolitik angewendet auf die staatlichen Zustände Deutschlands," written in 1853, serves as the foundational exposition of this concept. Ludwig von Rochau, a publicist and advocate for liberal political reform, coined the term in 1853 and further elaborated on his ideas in a second volume published in 1869. During this transformative period, Rochau, who had experienced exile in Paris during the 1848 revolution, gained prominence within the National Liberal Party.

Rochau's journey to the development of Realpolitik was influenced by the liberal advancements and ideals of the 1848 revolutions, which were ultimately overshadowed by authoritarian regimes and societal forces such as class divisions, religious fervor, and nationalism. Historian John Bew argues that Realpolitik emerged as an early attempt to reconcile liberal enlightened objectives with the complex dynamics of statecraft and power politics in mid-19th century Europe. Rochau's contemplation of the reasons behind the failure of liberal ideals led him to

astutely recognize that might should not be equated with right. He emphasized the pragmatic approach, stating that "to bring down the walls of Jericho, the Realpolitiker knows the simple pickaxe is more useful than the mightiest trumpet."

As Rochau's visionary concept gained traction among German intellectuals in the mid to late 19th century, it became closely associated with Otto von Bismarck's shrewd statecraft during the unification of Germany. Bismarck's success in achieving German unification further solidified the association of Realpolitik with practical, power-driven diplomacy. However, it's important to note that by 1890, the term Realpolitik had begun to diverge from its original connotations, as it became increasingly detached from its roots. This evolution marked a significant departure from the original essence of Realpolitik, as it transitioned from a response to the challenges of realizing liberal enlightened objectives to a broader and more pragmatic approach to politics and diplomacy.

Political Realism in International Relations: A Theoretical Lens

In the realm of international relations, the term "Realpolitik" pertains to the practical application of political strategies. In contrast, the concept of political realism within the domain of international relations embodies a theoretical framework dedicated to elucidating the dynamics of global events. The foundation of political realism rests upon the premise that states, acting as key actors on the international stage, advance their objectives by engaging in Realpolitik. Conversely, Realpolitik can be construed as the implementation of policies aligning with established tenets of political realism. In both instances, the fundamental supposition posits that policy formulation primarily hinges on the pursuit, acquisition, and utilization of power.

However, it is noteworthy that certain scholars within the realm of international relations realism, exemplified by figures like Kenneth Waltz, have opted to interpret state policies through a different lens. They underscore the pursuit of survival or security as the paramount motive, distinguishing it from the single-minded pursuit of power for its own sake.

Historical Foundations and Key Figures in the Development of Realpolitik

The historical evolution of Realpolitik and its key figures can be traced back to influential precursors and intellectual forefathers who laid the groundwork for contemporary diplomacy and modern international relations. Among these early contributors, Sun Tzu, the Chinese military

strategist known for "The Art of War," offered prescient insights that foreshadowed elements of Realpolitik. Additionally, Thucydides, the Greek historian renowned for his "History of the Peloponnesian War," is often cited as a significant intellectual forefather of Realpolitik. In the Indian context, Chanakya, an early statesman and author of the "Arthashastra," provided valuable contributions to political thought. Meanwhile, Ibn Khaldun, an Arab historiographer, played a foundational role in modern historiography with his comprehensive work, the "Muqaddimah."

One key thread of Realpolitik emerged through the works of thinkers like Han Fei in ancient China, who formulated Legalism and emphasized a ruler's covert control over the executive through ministers responsible for policy implementation. Niccolò Machiavelli, the Italian political philosopher, further expanded on the pursuit of power as a ruler's primary objective, regardless of religious or ethical considerations, in "Il Principe." Cardinal Richelieu, the French statesman, strategically positioned France as a dominant force in foreign affairs, exemplifying early modern Realpolitik.

In the 17th and 18th centuries, Thomas Hobbes, the English philosopher, characterized the state of nature as a "war of all against all" in his work "Leviathan," laying the groundwork for political realism. Frederick the Great, the Prussian monarch, combined strategic warfare and diplomacy to transform Prussia into a formidable European power. Charles Maurice de Talleyrand-Périgord, a distinguished French diplomat, demonstrated astute finesse in navigating the complex political systems of France and Europe.

During the 19th century, Prince Klemens Wenzel von Metternich, the Austrian statesman, staunchly opposed political revolutions, advocating for stability in a changing world. Carl von Clausewitz, the Prussian general and military strategist, made significant contributions to military theory with his seminal work "On War." Camillo Benso of Cavour, the Italian statesman, orchestrated diplomatic maneuvers that led to the unification of Italy and the rise of the Kingdom of Sardinia as a significant European power.

Moving into the modern era, Otto von Bismarck, the Prussian statesman, introduced the concept of the "balance of power" as a means to preserve peace, emphasizing the importance of power equilibrium in diplomatic strategies. In the 20th century, champions of political realism such as Hans Morgenthau, Henry Kissinger, and George F. Kennan, along with notable politicians like Charles de Gaulle and Lee Kuan Yew, continued to shape the landscape of international relations through Realpolitik principles.

Critics of Realpolitik, however, found fault in Mao Zedong's "Three Worlds Theory," contending that it lacked a robust ideological foundation and was primarily employed to rationalize diplomatic overtures with the Western world, highlighting the ongoing debate surrounding the nature and morality of Realpolitik in the realm of international politics.

China's Enduring Tradition of Realistic Governance

Long preceding the contemporary terminology of Realpolitik, China boasts a profound tradition of practical governance that spans millennia. Often recognized as Chinese Legalism, this pragmatic approach to governance finds resonance in Western awareness through seminal texts like "The Art of War." China's administrative practices exerted a substantial influence not only on other Asian nations but also on Western administrative systems, with its impact discernible as early as the 12th century. This influence played a pivotal role in shaping the foundations of the modern state, exemplified by the utilization of civil service examinations as a means of entry into the bureaucracy.

Commencing during the Spring and Autumn period, a cadre of pragmatic reformers emerged, driven by the pursuit of material gains for their respective states. The Qin state, notably, laid the cornerstone for the first Chinese Empire, the Qin Dynasty, in 221 BCE, effectively concluding China's tumultuous Warring States era. The political theories that emerged during this epoch, including the tenets of Confucianism, left an indelible mark on subsequent dynasties, leaving an enduring legacy.

Within this landscape, those categorized as Legalists epitomize a more unequivocally Realpolitik-oriented approach, distinct from the ideals of Confucianism. Among them, the school of thought derived from Shen Pu-hai offers a political technique emphasizing passive observation for factual determination, relieving the ruler of the need to assume an excessive personal role. Sinologist Herrlee G. Creel offers a provocative perspective, suggesting that one could arguably translate Shen Buhai's concept of Shu, or technique, as "science," even suggesting that Pu-hai could be considered the progenitor of political science, albeit with reservations. For instance, during the Warring States period, Duke Xiang of Song, when confronted with the opportunity to attack the enemy force as they crossed a river, chose instead to adhere to this method of passive observation.

However, it is worth noting that the Qin Dynasty, in stark contrast, deviated from this military tradition, capitalizing on the vulnerabilities of their adversaries to shape the course of history.

Germany's Nuanced Perspective on Realpolitik

In the United States, the term Realpolitik is often equated with power politics, carrying a somewhat negative undertone. In contrast, within Germany, Realpolitik bears a less pejorative connotation, denoting a pragmatic approach to politics as opposed to an idealistic one. Its historical association primarily emerges from the fervent era of 19th-century nationalism. Realpolitik strategies came into prominence as responses to the failures of the 1848 revolutions, aimed at bolstering state authority and fortifying social order.

The most renowned advocate of Realpolitik in Germany, Otto von Bismarck, exhibited a distinctive prowess in discerning what was realistically attainable and the strategic means to achieve it. Serving as the first Chancellor to Wilhelm I of the Kingdom of Prussia, Bismarck harnessed the principles of Realpolitik to realize Prussian dominance within the German sphere. He adroitly manipulated contentious political issues, such as the Schleswig-Holstein Question and the Hohenzollern candidature, deliberately provoking other nations and even resorting to warfare if necessary to secure his objectives. Such tactics exemplify Bismarck's pragmatic engagement with the authentic political landscape.

Furthermore, Bismarck's willingness to embrace select social policies championed by socialist movements, such as employee insurance and pensions, is a notable facet of his Realpolitik approach. In doing so, he introduced incremental changes from the top-down, strategically averting the potential for substantial bottom-up societal transformation. Similarly, Prussia's seemingly unconventional decision not to seek territorial concessions from a defeated Austria, a move that eventually paved the way for German unification, stands as a frequently cited exemplar of Realpolitik in action.

Singapore's Pragmatic Visionary: Lee Kuan Yew

Lee Kuan Yew, the inaugural Prime Minister of Singapore, has earned widespread recognition from political analysts for his pragmatic approach to governance. His policies, characterized by astute pragmatism, played a pivotal role in shaping Singapore's trajectory as a nation. Central to his philosophy was the belief that Singapore, a relatively diminutive nation among its neighbors,

could only thrive by establishing a clear contrast. This contrast was built on the foundation of a highly efficient and corruption-free government, complemented by a meritocratic civil service. In parallel, Lee advocated for Singapore's neutrality while concurrently cultivating a formidable military capability, perceiving it as a safeguard for the nation's independence given its strategic location. Emphatically endorsing Asian values, Lee contended that these values, distinct from Western ideals, were indispensable for the nation's prosperity. This set of values encompassed collectivism and communitarianism.

Lee's conceptualization of Singapore's only intrinsic resources as the resilience and strong work ethic of its people permeated all ethnic groups within the nation. Although he initially aligned with left-wing ideologies during his youth, his leadership witnessed a notable shift towards conservatism, with the conviction that extensive state welfare and subsidies could potentially stifle individual ambition.

In 1975, Chan Heng Chee characterized Singapore as a depoliticized "administrative state," where rational and scientific modes of public administration triumphed over ideology and politics. This perspective suggests that Singapore, by emphatically branding itself as pragmatic, conceals its underlying ideological and political nature, perpetuating an image of a politics-free landscape. Chua Beng Huat, in 1995, argued that the rhetoric of pragmatism in Singapore is itself ideological and hegemonic, systematically propagated by the People's Action Party government and institutionalized across all state functions, including administration, planning, and policy-making.

Lee Kuan Yew's political acumen and pragmatic insight garnered acclaim from world leaders. Former U.S. President Barack Obama acknowledged and valued his wisdom, while former Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe, a proponent of Asian values, hailed Lee as one of the preeminent leaders in modern Asian history and an architect of Singapore's contemporary prosperity. Tony Abbott, former Australian Prime Minister, characterized Lee as a towering figure in the region and credited him with Singapore's remarkable success. Henry Kissinger acknowledged Lee as one of the world's most accomplished pragmatists. Today, Lee's ideologies and perspectives continue to influence the curriculum at the Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy, an autonomous postgraduate institution at the National University of Singapore.

United Kingdom: Liberal Realism and the Rejection of Utopianism

E. H. Carr, a left-leaning British historian and scholar in international relations, embraced the philosophy of liberal realism, advocating for practical, real-world policies rather than utopian ideals. Carr's interpretation of realism revolved around the principle that the prevailing state of affairs is inherently correct. Consequently, in the realm of politics, he contended that realism entails the absence of moral judgments, with the measure of rightness determined solely by success, and wrongness by failure.

Carr held a firm conviction that the Bolsheviks were destined to triumph in the Russian Civil War. Grounded in Realpolitik, he supported British Prime Minister David Lloyd George's stance opposing War Secretary Winston Churchill's advocacy for military aid to the anti-Bolshevik White movement. Carr perceived Churchill's backing of the anti-Bolshevik forces as misguided, as he foresaw a resurgence of Russia as a major power under Bolshevik leadership.

Realpolitik in the United States: A Pragmatic Evolution

The emergence of American Realpolitik found its roots in the 1960s under the influence of Polish-American strategist Zbigniew Brzezinski, who would later serve as National Security Adviser to President Jimmy Carter. This marked a departure from the McCarthy-era antagonism and John Foster Dulles's rhetoric of military "liberation" in the Eastern Bloc. Brzezinski, while advising Presidents John F. Kennedy and Lyndon B. Johnson, advocated a strategy of "peaceful engagement" with the Soviet Union.

In sharp contrast to promoting anti-Soviet propaganda, Brzezinski believed in engaging in frequent interactions with communist regimes and their populations. He recognized the economic hardships endured in the Eastern Bloc, characterized by perpetual shortages of goods. He saw their alignment with the Soviet Union as a historical necessity rather than an ideological choice. Brzezinski proposed enticing these nations through economic incentives, educational and cultural exchanges aimed at intellectuals, and showing favoritism toward regimes displaying signs of liberalization or reduced reliance on Moscow. This approach offered a pragmatic and evolution-based alternative to empty political rhetoric.

The formal introduction of Realpolitik to the White House is often attributed to Henry Kissinger during his tenure as Secretary of State under President Richard Nixon. For Kissinger, Realpolitik

meant pragmatic dealings with powerful nations, free from rigid political doctrine or ethical constraints. A prime example was Nixon's diplomatic outreach to the People's Republic of China, a move made despite American opposition to communism and the previous containment doctrine. Additionally, Kissinger employed shuttle diplomacy after the 1973 Arab-Israeli war, persuading Israel to partially withdraw from the Sinai, acknowledging the political realities shaped by the oil crisis.

Kissinger himself disclaimed the term Realpolitik and noted its use by both liberal and realist foreign policy thinkers, often as a label or criticism. He viewed his actions as a statesman, guided by an understanding of the actual balance of power to achieve his objectives.

This flexible and pragmatic approach, informed by Realpolitik principles, has influenced American policy without becoming standard doctrine. Instead, it has been characterized by adaptability, adjusting to the exigencies of each situation. This approach persisted through subsequent administrations, exemplified by Rahm Emanuel's characterization of President Barack Obama's policies as pragmatic and akin to those of George H.W. Bush.

Realpolitik, distinct from ideological politics, is inherently goal-oriented and adaptable, guided by practical necessities rather than fixed rules. This approach often involves compromises on ideological principles to secure broader national interests. During the Cold War, the United States frequently supported authoritarian regimes with poor human rights records in pursuit of regional stability. This practice continued even after the Cold War.

In recent times, former Ambassador Dennis Ross advocated for a Realpolitik approach to foreign policy in his 2007 book "Statecraft: And How to Restore America's Standing in the World." Contrasting with political ideologues who prioritize principles over practical considerations, Realpolitik is characterized by a willingness to compromise for the sake of long-term national interests.

Pakistan's Realpolitik Approach and Relations with the US in the 1970s

The relations between Pakistan and the United States during the 1970s were characterized by a complex interplay of factors, prominently featuring Pakistan's assertive pursuit of a nuclear program, driven by a Realpolitik approach.

Against the backdrop of the Iranian Revolution, President Jimmy Carter sought to improve relations with Pakistan. In 1977, General Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq assumed power in Pakistan after the imposition of Martial Law in response to political turmoil. Recognizing the immediate strategic advantages that Pakistan could gain by aligning with the United States amid the Soviet-Afghan War, Zia embarked on a path that exemplified a Realpolitik approach.

Pakistan's strategic geopolitical location made it a subject of profound interest to the United States. In response, the U.S. provided substantial financial and military assistance to Pakistan, including the provision of General Dynamics F-16 Fighting Falcon aircraft and financial aid during the Soviet–Afghan War, all within the framework of a Realpolitik strategy.

Initially, General Zia declined a \$400 million aid package from the U.S., dismissing it as inconsequential. However, when Ronald Reagan assumed office and sought to augment funding for Operation Cyclone and support for Pakistan, the two nations agreed on a substantial \$3.2 billion military and economic assistance package, emblematic of their shared Realpolitik approach.

Under Zia's leadership, Pakistan played a pivotal role in training Afghan mujahideen, aligning its efforts with Operation Cyclone to counter the Soviet-backed government in Afghanistan. Notably, Pakistan maintained diplomatic ties with the Soviet Union during the Afghan conflict, a diplomatic maneuver grounded in pragmatic Realpolitik considerations rather than a genuine partnership.

One of the most significant Realpolitik decisions of Zia-ul-Haq's presidency centered around Pakistan's nuclear program. In the face of international pressure and the looming threat of sanctions, Zia pursued a Realpolitik approach, prioritizing national interests over international non-proliferation norms. The development of nuclear weapons was deemed essential to deter Pakistan's historical rival, India, which had successfully conducted nuclear tests in 1974. This calculated move underscored the pragmatic considerations that often shape international relations within the realm of Realpolitik.

Conclusion:

In the exploration of Realpolitik across various geopolitical contexts, one overarching theme emerges: the pragmatic pursuit of national interests in the realm of international relations. Realpolitik, a term often associated with realism and pragmatism, transcends ideological boundaries and calls for an approach grounded in practicality and the pursuit of power or security.

The United States, for instance, witnessed the evolution of its foreign policy towards Realpolitik during the 1960s and beyond. Influenced by figures like Zbigniew Brzezinski and Henry Kissinger, American leaders recognized the need for flexible and pragmatic approaches in dealing with other nations. This shift away from rigid doctrine and ideology allowed for more effective engagement on the global stage. The emphasis was placed on engaging with regimes and populations under communist rule rather than promoting anti-Soviet propaganda. It was a pragmatic acknowledgment of the economic realities within these nations, as well as their historical ties to the Soviet Union.

Pakistan's experience during the 1970s provides a vivid illustration of Realpolitik in action. General Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq's leadership embodied a Realpolitik approach as he navigated the complex terrain of international relations. Pakistan's strategic importance in the context of the Soviet-Afghan War made it a subject of significant interest to the United States. Realizing the potential benefits of aligning with the U.S., Zia sought financial and military support, even as he maintained diplomatic ties with the Soviet Union. Zia's decisive role in Pakistan's nuclear program underscored the prioritization of national interests over international non-proliferation norms—a classic example of Realpolitik in practice.

In the case of Singapore, Lee Kuan Yew's pragmatic policies epitomized Realpolitik principles. Recognizing the need for Singapore to distinguish itself in the global arena, he pursued effective governance and a non-corrupt civil service under a meritocratic system. His approach emphasized building a strong military capability as a guarantor of independence, while advocating for Asian values in a rapidly changing world. Lee's pragmatism and commitment to real-world solutions shaped Singapore's success as a nation.

These examples reflect the essence of Realpolitik—a willingness to compromise on ideology and prioritize practical exigencies. This approach, often centered on the pursuit of power or security,

has been instrumental in shaping international relations. It acknowledges that in a world characterized by shifting dynamics and complex challenges, the pursuit of national interests requires adaptability and realism.

In conclusion, Realpolitik serves as a pragmatic guide in the intricate landscape of international relations. It reminds us that while ideologies and principles have their place, they must often yield to the imperatives of national interest and real-world circumstances. As history has shown, the leaders and nations that master the art of Realpolitik are often better positioned to navigate the complexities of a rapidly changing world.

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